

PIMTABSA: A Personality influenced Multitask model for Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis using LSTM

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Abstract: In the expanding field of sentiment analysis, the integration of personality prediction into aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) represents a novel and promising approach to enhance the accuracy and depth of sentiment detection. This paper proposes a unique framework that leverages the Big Five personality traits (Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism) alongside Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, under a multitask learning paradigm, to improve the performance of ABSA. This is, to the best of knowledge, the first work considering the use of personality traits as auxiliary tasks in order to capture the manifold subtle ways in which personality would influence the expression of sentiment towards the different aspects of products or services. And then, model uses the LSTM component to model the sequential character of the text, which makes the extraction accurate in terms of the aspect terms and sentiment polarities. The proposed model designs a multitask learning strategy simultaneously to predict sentiments and personality traits. Such joint learning will allow enhancing the model's understanding of textual context and sentiment expression. Thorough experiments on many benchmark datasets show that the proposed approach is competitive with the state of the art for the aspect-based sentiment analysis and provides some of the deepest insights into personality predictions. Model has obtained F1-scores of 79.78%, 83.67%, and 88.80 % on the Twitter, Laptop, and Restaurant datasets, respectively. These results highlight a significant improvement over existing methods in the literature. For instance, our model outperformed traditional approaches like RAM, which achieved 69.36% on the Twitter dataset, and even advanced techniques such as DualGCN+Bert, which scored 77.4% on Twitter. It can be generally concluded that this research finally opens the way to a new and meaningful opportunity for sentiment analysis applications: integrated into ABSA models, personality prediction advances applications ranging from personalized recommendation systems to the nuance market analysis tools. As far as we know this study is the first attempt to utilise personality feature to enhance sentiment prediction tasks.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, ABSA, Personality traits, Multitasking, Big 5, OCEAN, Deep Learning

Categories: I.2, I.2.7, I.7

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1 Introduction

Sentiment analysis is a revolutionary tool that helps bring sentiment out of a sea of unstructured text and allows a much more potent means of development. This covers a broad range of platforms, such as online banking transactions, blogs, reviews, social network updates, conversations, and e-commerce feedback. As a digital pulse, it reads public feeling on social networks, hence simplifying the once clunky task of gathering public opinion and feedback via traditional channels. Practically, sentiment analysis is a classification that is traditionally used to classify user comments into two overly simplified binary classifications: positive or negative. It totally disregards the fact that emotions and opinions of people are of an extremely fine and complex nature; hence, the value of analyses should be even more fine. In fact, often the content users produce online is trusted more than the information offered to them by vendors. Such insights are invaluable for enhancing product quality, fostering innovation, and assessing societal impacts.

Research by Hu and Liu [Hu, 04] elaborates on and formalizes the document-level and aspect-level categories in sentiment analysis. The three main levels of sentiment analysis are document-level, sentence-level, and aspect-level. Each one gives the researcher a very different way in which he may scope out that sentiment, from the very broad type, like in a document, to the much finer aspect-based evaluations.

Sentiment analysis has a broad range of applications, including financial forecasting [Khaidem, 16] and political analysis [Tumasjan, 10], e-health [Cambria, 10] and e-tourism sectors [Valdivia, 17], profiling users [Zhang, 16] and assessing user influence, detecting online communities [Shen, 14], and enhancing dialogue systems [Young, 17].

In aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA), there are two main subtasks Aspect Term Extraction and Sentiment detection. The goal is to identify not just the sentiment (positive, negative, neutral) expressed in a text, but also the specific aspects or features that the sentiment is directed towards. For instance, in a restaurant review, the sentiment might be positive towards the food ("The sushi was excellent") but negative towards the service ("The waiters were unfriendly"). This granular approach helps in understanding complex consumer sentiments across various texts, such as reviews and social media comments.

For sentiment analysis, ABSA first depended on the then available traditional machine learning techniques like Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines, and Logistic Regression, which used classifiers to learn to read customer reviews based on such linguistic features, primarily, these techniques focused on high frequency occurring nouns or phrases that encapsulated the emotional nature of the reviews. But, the fallacies are the fact that not all words are sentimental and that some very distinguishing features were not discussed very often. Later, new work concentrated on neural networks that consider text as a sequence of words. The various neural networks, that it has suggested, include Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) (Nadeem et al., 2023), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks, and Convolution-based Networks (Nadeem et al., 2022). However, the issues of maintaining syntactic correctness and the treatment of word dependencies in the long term are also issues for these sophisticated models.

Research suggests that the emotional expressions of individuals can indicate certain aspects of their personalities [Colin, 07]. For example, frequent and positive social media posters are likely to be more extroverted, while those who post often with a negative tone may tend to be more neurotic. Additionally, individuals who frequently convey their emotions through writing are generally more expressive emotionally. By analysing text for language patterns and emotional expressions, it's possible to link personality traits with sentiment classifiers, particularly in the prediction of sentiment from brief text samples based on personality.

For example consider the following tweet and review:

Tweet: "Just tried the new Korean fusion restaurant—what an explosion of flavors! Love exploring new cuisines! #FoodieAdventures"

This tweet demonstrates the positive sentiment and openness to new experiences, with a focus on exploration and excitement about novel ideas.

Review: "I'm really disappointed with my hotel room. It's noisy, the bed is uncomfortable, and I'm worried I won't get any sleep at all. Totally not what I was expecting. 😞"

This review reflects high neuroticism, focusing on the negative aspects and expressing anxiety and dissatisfaction, common in those with this personality trait.

Big 5 Personality Traits

Figure 1: Big 5 Personality Traits

In the proposed work, it is found that personality trait of the users impacts the aspect-based sentiment extraction positively. Moreover, this is the novel model that used

personality for sentiment detection using multitask learning approach. Researchers have used multitask learning for sentiment detection [Wang, 23],[Qian, 23] but have not considered the users' personality features. Both sentiment detection and personality prediction are performed simultaneously where the performance of both predictions have significantly improved.

The highlights of this paper are as follows:

- PIMTABSA : A innovative multitask learning Personality Based Sentiment Analysis model that predicts sentiment based on aspects and personality features.
- Additionally, the proposed work predicts big 5 personality traits simultaneously with good accuracy.
- Evidence that PIMTABSA performs well on analysing the results with state of art algorithms.

2 Related Works

The field is evolving, with significant progress in detecting entities or aspects within documents and aggregating sentiment on them for various applications [Schouten, 16]. ABSA primarily involves aspect and sentiment extraction as well as determining the orientation of the sentiment; newer models concentrate on aspect sentiment pair extraction and rating prediction [Gojali, 16]. In an effort to study people's thoughts at the aspect level, recent developments in ABSA have introduced tasks for assessing many sentiment parts and their relationships, greatly enhancing comprehension of compound ABSA tasks [Gojali, 16], [Madhoushi, 19]. It has been demonstrated that inter-aspect dependencies can be effectively included into sentiment analysis to provide a more accurate classification of sentiments toward several aspects inside a sentence [Hazarika, 18]. With the help of glove word vectors that simultaneously identify aspect terms, sentiment polarities, and opinion terms, Yan et al.'s sequence-to-sequence text generation method can selectively output aspect terms, sentiment polarity, and corresponding opinion items of input sentences [Yan, 23]. The results are then normalized. Aspect-Based Financial Sentiment Analysis in the financial domain utilizes deep learning for aspect detection and sentiment analysis, showcasing direct applications in the financial sector [Hitkul, 18]. The creation of adaptive aspect-based lexicons for ABSA has been explored to improve classification accuracy by adapting general lexicons to aspect-based contexts [Mowlaei, 20]. A feature distillation network (FDN) proposed by Shuang et.al for ABSA aims to reduce noise and distill aspect-relevant sentiment features in context words [Shuang, 20].

BERT is commonly used for a variety of NLP tasks due to the rise of transformers in the field. It has been pre-trained on a large amount of unlabelled text, including the full Wikipedia with its 2.5 billion words, and a large Book Corpus, containing more than 800 million words. This initial training phase is crucial, accounting for much of BERT's effectiveness. As it trains on large datasets, the model begins to grasp the finer, more intricate elements of language operation, making it versatile for numerous NLP applications. [Chavan, 22]

An additional CNN layer has been integrated into the original BERT framework [J.Dong, 20] to enhance its precision, resulting in the BERT-CNN sentiment analysis

model. This model demonstrated significant improvements in F1 scores when used to analyze the sentiment of online product reviews, outperforming both standalone CNN and original BERT models. BERT's capabilities are explored in target-dependent sentiment categorization within Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) [Z. Gao, 19], and a universal classifier model [Mickel, 19] has been proposed that leverages BERT's pre-trained contextual word representations to assess semantic similarities through sentence pair classification.

Another approach evaluates the sentiment polarity of news articles by analyzing the frequency of positive and negative words using statistical methods [Vishal, 17]. A detailed review of the pros and cons of various cutting-edge techniques provides a thorough examination of the current challenges and scenarios in this area [Prabha, 19]. All above models concentrated on single task. Currently multitasking has gained importance compared to single task. Multitask learning (MTL) has recently gained prominence for its ability to enhance model performance by identifying similarities and differences across tasks [Fortin, 19]. Originally introduced by Caruana, one popular strategy employs a shared-bottom architecture, which, despite reducing overfitting risks, may create optimization challenges due to task heterogeneity. To address these challenges, constraints have been placed on specific task parameters. In contexts with scarce data, Duong et al. have applied L-2 regularization across diverse task parameters. Similarly, Misra et al. developed cross-stitch networks to facilitate the learning of linear combinations of task-specific embeddings, proving effective in fields such as image-based surface normal prediction and semantic segmentation.

Tensor factorization, as implemented by Yang et al. [Yang, 16], improved task-specific performance; however, due to its complex nature, it demands a substantial volume of training data. Similarly, Ma et al. [Jiaqi Ma, 18] employed a multi-gate mixture-of-experts model, necessitating numerous experts to discern various task components, with the most crucial feature being selected based on the top gate score, underscoring the need for extensive data.

LSTM, in contrast to regular RNN, uses a sequence of gates to implement the "remember" mechanism, which lessens the gradient disappearance issue and makes it specifically tailored for controlling long-term dependencies. Tasks where the context across extended sequences can significantly impact outcomes, like speech recognition, language translation, and time-series forecasting, require temporal modeling. LSTM excels in temporal modeling to encode the long-distance dependency of the given input as stated in [Tan Kian, 22].

The main advantage of LSTM networks lies in their structure of memory cells controlled by three gates—input gate, forget gate and output gate. These gates regulate the flow of information, determining which data to retain and which to forget. This architecture prevents the vanishing gradient problem, a common issue in standard RNNs, where gradients diminish as they propagate backward through time. LSTMs overcome this issue by maintaining a constant error flow, allowing them to remember patterns over many time steps [Sepp Hochreiter, 97]. Because they can accommodate long-term dependencies without experiencing appreciable performance deterioration, LSTMs also perform better than other recurrent network techniques. This makes them particularly useful for solving complex tasks like language modeling, sentiment analysis, and even intricate tasks in robotics and control systems where understanding sequential data is crucial.

In contrast, this paper introduces a new multitask learning framework that combines BERT and LSTM to detect sentiment and personality traits. This approach seeks to overcome the limitations of previous models by focusing on task-specific learning without the need for a large amount of training data. A significant hurdle remains in securing a multilabelled dataset for training purposes. Therefore, the model has opted to utilize several datasets, each dedicated to personality and sentiment label detection.

3 Proposed Model

This research introduces a multitasking strategy utilizing a BERT and LSTM approach to address two distinct tasks: 1. Personality Prediction and 2. Sentiment Analysis. The multi-task learning model leverages the insights gained from training on one task to minimize the loss on other tasks within the training network. This transfer of knowledge typically results in a unified model capable of making multiple predictions, often with improved accuracy compared to training separate models for each task [Christopher, 21]. The performance of the model is notably better when the tasks are interrelated. Additionally, the model can lessen the overfitting risk by using a shared hidden layer. This method is employed in the prediction strategy.

3.1 Datasets Description

The three benchmark datasets used for this research are the SemEval 2014 Task 4 datasets, which include reviews of laptops and restaurants [Pontiki, 14], the ACL 14 Twitter dataset [Dong, 14] and MyPersonality dataset [Colin, 07].

The SemEval-2014 Task 4 dataset is typically divided into two main parts:

Laptop Reviews: Contains reviews of laptops, extracted from online sources, annotated with sentiments towards various aspects of the laptops mentioned in the reviews.

Restaurant Reviews: Comprises reviews of restaurants, also annotated with sentiments towards different aspects of the dining experience, such as food, service, and ambiance.

These datasets are annotated at both the aspect term level (identifying specific phrases that denote aspects) and the aspect polarity (classifying sentiments into broader categories related to the product or service). Three aspect polarity labels are used namely neutral, negative, and positive. Researchers and developers use this dataset to train and evaluate their models on the task of aspect-based sentiment analysis, helping improve the granularity with which sentiment analysis tools understand and process user opinions.

The Twitter dataset, collected from social media, captures public opinions on trending current events. Each of these datasets features a corpus rich in emotional content expressed by the users. The statistics of sentiment and personality datasets are provided in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. The data is not equally balanced for all sentiments as shown in figure 2. The positive data is very high in restaurant dataset and neutral data is very high in twitter dataset, whereas neutral data are low in laptop dataset. So, a model that can handle this unbalance of sentiment data has to be developed.

Domain	Restaurant		Laptop		Twitter	
	Tr	T	Tr	T	Tr	T
P	2164	728	987	341	1561	173
N	805	196	866	128	1560	173
Neu	633	196	460	169	3127	346

Table 1: Distribution of sentiment data (Tr-training data T-Testing data)

Figure 2: Dataset Analysis

Trait	Yes		No	
	No. of users	No. of status	No. of users	No. of status
O	176	7370	74	2547
C	130	4556	120	5361
E	96	4210	154	5707
A	134	5268	116	4649
N	99	3717	151	6200

Table 2: Distribution of personality traits data

The model employed the MyPersonality dataset, which comprises 9,917 statuses from 250 users. Collected in 2007, this data originates from a Facebook application designed

for psychological research, where participants completed a personality questionnaire. The dataset is structured to include raw textual content from Facebook status updates, author information, and personality labels (both scores and categories). Additionally, it features metrics related to the social networks of users, such as network size, betweenness, density, brokerage, and transitivity, which help deduce personality characteristics.

3.2 Proposed Model-PIMTABSA

The model has used the above personality dataset to use its features in predicting sentiment of semeval datasets. Initially, the dataset undergoes preprocessing where token embeddings are generated using the BERT-base approach. This begins with the removal of any URLs starting with "http://" or "https://." Subsequently, the NLTK package is employed to eliminate select stop words, followed by the removal of unique non-standard symbols not classified as punctuation, digits, or letters.

The BERT model receives the input data and uses the Transformer architecture and the self-attention mechanism intensively. A position-wise completely connected feed-forward network and a multi-head self-attention mechanism are the main parts of the Transformer block. For processing the token sequence in BERT, multiple Transformer blocks are arranged sequentially. The multi-head self-attention mechanism can simultaneously focus on several portions of the input sequence and switch between them based on which part is relevant to the handling of the given token at that specific moment. This facilitates an understanding of context and word relationships within sentences.

As the Transformer architecture inherently lacks any recognition of token order, BERT incorporates positional embeddings with its input embeddings to account for token positions in the sequence. These embeddings are summed with token embeddings before they are processed by the Transformer blocks. Token embeddings are vector representations derived from the initial embedding layer. Each token from the textual input is converted into a vector and then used as input to the model. For tasks involving multiple sequences, like question-answering, BERT employs segment embeddings to differentiate between sequences. Each LSTM takes as input the sequence of token embeddings from BERT's output. Input to both LSTMs is the hidden size from the BERT model (`self.base_model.config.hidden_size`), and the output dimension is set to 768. The personality LSTM processes the sequence to extract features relevant to predicting personality traits. The sentiment LSTM does the same for sentiment prediction. The hidden states from the LSTMs are passed through fully connected (linear) layers which returns the logits for both personality traits and sentiment in the form of two separate outputs.

Weighted loss function is used to handle imbalanced sentiment classes as mentioned in Section 3.1. Based on the distribution of data, the weights are either increased or decreased. Positive sentiment is overrepresented in restaurant dataset, so the weights for neutral and negative sentiments is increased. Neutral sentiment is underrepresented in Laptop dataset, so its weight is increased. Similarly, Neutral sentiment is highly represented in twitter dataset, so its weight is reduced. Regularization techniques like Dropout and L2 regularization are used to reduce overfitting. Task specific weights are used to balance and prioritize the sentiment analysis task over the personality prediction

task. The hyperparameters are given in Table 3 and complete model configuration is illustrated in Figure 3.

Parameters	Proposed model	Description
Tasks	Personality Trait Prediction, Sentiment Analysis	Predict personality traits and classify the sentiment of text.
Input Features	BERT Sentence Embeddings (768-dimensional vector)	Pretrained BERT model (bert-base-uncased) used to generate input features.
Shared Layer	BERT's last hidden state (sequence output)	BERT output is shared as input to two LSTMs for different tasks.
Personality LSTM	LSTM (768 input units, 768 hidden units, batch_first=True)	Connected to BERT output, processes sequence for personality trait prediction.
Sentiment LSTM	LSTM (768 input units, 768 hidden units, batch_first=True)	Connected to BERT output, processes sequence for sentiment classification.
Personality Dense Layer	Dense Layer (5 output units, 768 input units)	Fully connected layer for personality trait prediction, outputs logits for 5 traits.
Sentiment Dense Layer	Dense Layer (3 output units, 768 input units)	Fully connected layer for sentiment classification, outputs logits for 3 sentiment classes.
Dropout	Dropout (p=0.3)	Applied to the BERT hidden state output to prevent overfitting.
Output	Personality logits (5), Sentiment logits (3)	Final outputs are personality trait logits and sentiment logits, passed without explicit activation.
Activation Functions	Sigmoid (for personality traits), Softmax (for sentiment)	Sigmoid applied via BCEWithLogitsLoss for personality; Softmax used in CrossEntropyLoss for sentiment.
Loss Function	BCEWithLogitsLoss (personality), CrossEntropyLoss (sentiment)	Loss functions used for multitask training, one for each task.
Epochs	60	The number of epochs for training.
Batch Size	16	The number of samples processed in each batch.
Optimizer	Adam (lr=2e-5, weight_decay=1e-2)	Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 2e-5 and L2 weight decay regularization of 1e-2 used for model parameter updates.
Task-Specific Weights	alpha = 0.4 (personality), beta = 0.6 (sentiment)	Weights used to balance the losses between personality and sentiment tasks.

Table 3: Hyperparameters with description

Figure 3: PIMTABSA- Proposed model

4 Evaluation Metrics

The model uses accuracy and f1 score metric techniques to analyse its performance.

4.1 F1 Score:

The computation process is demonstrated below. The confusion matrix is generated for each personality label by applying the strategy below in Table 4.

Actual Predicted	Positive	Negative
Positive	TP	FP
Negative	FN	TN

Table 4: Confusion Matrix

F1-Score is calculated using the given formula

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2PR}{P + R}$$

Where $P=TP/(TP+FP)$ and $R=TP/(TP+FN)$, P-Precision, R-Recall. TP-True Positive, TN-True Negative, FP-False Positive, FN-False Negative.

4.2 Accuracy:

This metric serves as an indicator of a model's performance, specifically highlighting its accuracy in correctly predicting both true positives and true negatives. It is particularly effective for evaluating class distribution in datasets where the classes are balanced.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

4.3 Loss

This metric is used to indicate more accurate model. Model with lower loss values serves better. Cross Entropy Loss is calculated for Sentiment Classification and BCE with Logits Loss (Binary Cross Entropy Loss With Sigmoid Function) is calculated for Personality prediction. Sentiment Classification loss is denoted as L2 and Personality Prediction loss is denoted as L1.

$$L1 = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [\log_e(1 + e^{-z}) + z(1 - y_i)] & \text{if } z > 0 \text{ then } t_n = 0 \\ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [\log_e(1 + e^z) - z \cdot y_i] & \text{otherwise, } t_n = -z \end{cases}$$

$$L2 = - \sum_i t_i \ln y_i$$

Task specific weights α and β are used to balance the contribution of each task to the overall loss during training. Overall loss of the proposed model is calculated as L using the formula given.

$$L = \alpha \times L1 + \beta \times L2$$

The Loss curve for the proposed model is shown in Figure 4. The test loss is only slightly higher than training loss indicating that model suits well for the datasets. This balance between test and training loss indicates that the model can generalize its learning.

Figure 4: Proposed Model's loss

5 Results and Discussions

The model's performance is compared with the baseline models as shown in Table 6. The approaches of baseline models are detailed in table 5.

Model Name	Methodology
RAM [Chen, 17]	Long-distance sentiment representations using Multi-attention mechanism.
MGAN [Fan, 18]	Interactions between aspect and context at the lexical level using a multi-grained attention mechanism.
ASGCN [Zhang, 19]	Syntactic information and word dependencies building a GCN based on dependency tree
CDT [Sun, 19]	GCN to identify the sentiment polarity of opinion words and learn aspect representations
BiGCN [Zhang, 20]	Hierarchical graph structure to encode corpus level word co-occurrence information
RGAT [Wang, 20]	Relational graph attention network encoding a new tree structure for sentiment prediction.
DGEDT [Tang, 20]	A dependency graph dual-transformer network using flat and graph-based representation.
DualGCN [Li, 21]	Dual graph convolutional networks simultaneously considering the complementarity of syntax structures and semantic correlations
BySyn-GAT [Liang, 22]	The sentiment-aware context of each aspect and the sentiment relationship between the various aspects using the constituent tree information.

Table 5: Baseline models considered for comparison

These techniques have greatly improved performance by using pre-trained language models. This phenomena demonstrates the effectiveness of language models that have

already been trained, as they can provide rich semantic characteristics to improve classification performance in subsequent trials. Thus, in order to learn the whole semantic representation of full sentences, we also use BERT as the base encoder. These findings also suggest that our proposed structure- PIMTABSA successfully combines syntactic and semantic data. PIMTABSA model has performed well on the three benchmark datasets in terms of accuracy and f1 score. The model utilizes the personality features and correlates it with the sentiment features for prediction. It is shown that these personality features highly influences sentiment prediction. The accuracy has increased by more than 1% in all the datasets. The model has improved by 2.12% in accuracy for Restaurant dataset. Similarly, F1 score has improved significantly in Twitter dataset compared to the other two.

Table 7 shows Review samples. It is seen that a single review with three different aspects and same polarity are classified better than a review with different polarity. But the model does perform well on different polarity classification on other sentences. It is only on multiple aspect and polarity detection, the model has to concentrate to improve its performance. Meanwhile, it is prudent that the proposed model performs well in all the benchmark datasets despite small hiccups. The models performance on train and test dataset is depicted in figure 7 for different domains. The test accuracy for Restaurant dataset starts much lower at 75.2%, but also shows consistent improvement over the epochs, reaching 83.75% by epoch 60. While there is a noticeable gap between the training and test accuracies indicating some degree of overfitting, the test accuracy does improve significantly. Generalization is better in the Restaurant and Twitter datasets, though improvements can still be made.

Model	Twitter	Laptop	Restaurant	Twitter	Laptop	Restaurant
	F1-Score			Accuracy		
RAM [Chen, 17]	69.36	74.49	80.23	67.30	71.35	70.80
MGAN [Fan, 18]	72.54	75.39	81.25	70.81	72.47	71.94
ASGCN [Zhang, 19]	72.15	75.55	80.77	70.40	71.05	72.02
CDT [Sun, 19]	74.66	77.19	82.30	73.66	72.99	74.02
BiGCN [Zhang, 20]	74.16	74.59	81.97	73.35	71.84	73.48
RGAT [Wang, 20]	75.57	77.42	83.30	73.82	73.76	76.08
DGEDT [Tang, 20]	74.80	76.80	83.90	73.40	72.30	75.10
DualGCN [Li, 21]	75.92	78.48	84.27	74.29	74.74	78.08
RGAT+Bert [Wang, 20]	76.15	78.21	86.60	74.88	74.07	81.35
DGEDT+Bert [Tang, 20]	77.90	79.80	86.30	75.40	75.60	80.00
DualGCN+Bert [Li, 21]	77.40	81.80	87.13	76.02	78.10	81.16

BySyn-GAT [Liang, 22]	77.99	82.44	87.49	76.80	79.15	81.63
Proposed Model- PIMTABSA	79.78	83.67	88.8	78.03	80.72	83.75

Table 6: Comparison with other baseline models' results. [Results are taken from their respective works]

The proposed model's performance is visualised in Figure 6. The confusion matrix of all the test datasets combined is visualised in Figure 8. Precision and Recall for each dataset is visualised in Figure 9. This proves that proposed model has achieved significant performance.

Review Samples	Aspect Term	Actual Labels	Predicted Labels
I am pleased with the fast log on , speedy WiFi connection and the long battery life -LRB- > 6 hrs -RRB- .	log on	positive	positive
	WiFi connection	positive	positive
	battery life	positive	positive
Other than not being a fan of click pads -LRB- industry standard these days -RRB- and the lousy internal speakers , it 's hard for me to find things about this notebook I don't like , especially considering the \$ 35neutral price tag .	internal speakers	negative	negative
	price tag	positive	negative
	click pads	negative	Negative
Has all the other features I wanted including a VGA port , HDMI , ethernet and 3 USB ports .	features	positive	positive
	VGA port	neutral	neutral
	HDMI	neutral	neutral
	ethernet	neutral	neutral
	USB ports	neutral	neutral
the latest version does not have a disc drive .	disc drive	neutral	negative
Screen - although some people might complain about low res which I think is ridiculous .	Screen	positive	negative
	res	positive	positive

The Apple engineers have not yet discovered the delete key .	delete key	negative	negative
I am still in the process of learning about its features .	features	neutral	neutral

Table 7: Review Samples with actual and predicted labels from SemEval14 dataset

Figure 6: Performance of Proposed Model with other models: Accuracy and F1 score

Figure 7: Accuracy of the proposed model on train and test datasets.

Figure 8: Confusion matrix

Figure 9: Precision and Recall

6 Conclusion

This study introduces a Personality influenced Multitask model for Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis using LSTM (PIMTABS). This model autonomously trains on sentiment analysis features through a multitask learning framework, simultaneously predicting personality traits and sentiments. The experiments, conducted using the SemEval-14, Twitter, and Facebook’s myPersonality datasets, demonstrate that

PIMTABSA outperforms conventional deep learning models in benchmark tests. With F1-scores of 79.78%, 83.67%, and 88.80 % on the Twitter, Laptop, and Restaurant datasets, respectively, and corresponding accuracy metrics, the proposed PIMTABSA model demonstrates excellent results. Its design, which makes use of pretrained BERT, LSTMs for task-specific feature extraction, multitask learning, and efficient handling of class imbalance, greatly enhances its predictive capabilities, making it a compelling advancement in sentiment analysis and personality trait prediction. Looking ahead, there is potential to enhance this model for multimodal contexts and additional languages, and to explore the integration of personality traits with sentiment analysis features. Implementing the proposed model also aids in pinpointing unique personality traits, which could be utilized to customize artificial intelligence systems.

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